
Dynamic Obstacle Detection for Blind People

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Abstract: *The Dynamic Obstacle Detection for the Blind people aims to create a technology that will help visually impaired individuals to navigate their environment more safely and independently. This system uses a combination of sensors and algorithms to detect and track moving objects in real-time, providing users with audio cues and alerts to help them avoid potential obstacles. The system is designed to be lightweight, portable, and easy to use, making it a valuable tool for blind individuals in a variety of settings. With improved mobility and independence, blind individuals can gain greater access to the world around them and experience a better quality of life. The potential benefits of this technology include increased safety, accessibility, and social engagement for visually impaired*

Keywords: Object Detection, Alert, Individual

1. Introduction

Performing daily tasks can also be a struggle for blind individuals. Simple tasks like cooking, cleaning, and getting dressed may require adaptations or assistance. Accessing information can also be challenging, as much of the world is designed for sighted individuals. Blind individuals may need alternative formats, such as braille or audio, to access information. One of the biggest challenges for blind people is mobility. Without the ability to see, navigating unfamiliar environments can be difficult and dangerous. Blind individuals may have to rely on other senses, such as hearing and touch, to move around safely. This can be especially challenging in crowded or noisy environments. Another challenge is communication. Blind individuals may have difficulty communicating with others who are not familiar with their needs or who do not know how to interact with a visually impaired person. This can lead to feelings of isolation and exclusion. A Dynamic Motion Detection for the Blind project can be incredibly helpful in the real world in a variety of ways. Here are some potential benefits such as Improved mobility and safety. By detecting and alerting the user to nearby objects or obstacles, this technology can help blind people navigate their surroundings more safely and independently. the goal is to have a better life for them and for them to be more independent. Blind individuals often need the assistance of others to navigate unfamiliar environments, by providing them with real-time information about their surroundings, this technology can reduce their reliance on others and help them gain more independence. It provides better accessibility i.e in many public spaces are not designed with the needs of blind individuals in mind. This technology can help make these spaces more accessible by providing users with information about their surroundings and potential obstacles.

2. Materials and Methods

Fig. 1. Block Diagram of system architecture

Fig. 1 specifies the general work flow of our system which is based on YOLOv3.

3.1. Dataset

The COCO (Common Objects in Context) dataset is a large-scale dataset for object detection, segmentation, and captioning. It contains more than 200,000 images, each labeled with the objects that appear in the image and their bounding box coordinates. The dataset also includes a number of additional annotations, such as segmentation masks for each object and captions describing the scene. The COCO dataset is widely used in research and has been a standard benchmark for evaluating the performance of object detection algorithms. It contains a diverse set of images, with objects of varying sizes, shapes, and poses. This makes it a challenging dataset for object detection algorithms, and a good test of their capabilities.

In addition to object detection, the COCO dataset is also used for tasks such as image segmentation and caption generation. It provides a rich set of annotations that can be used to train and evaluate models for these tasks.

3.2. Non-Maximum Suppression

Non-maximum suppression (NMS) is a technique used to suppress (i.e., remove) bounding boxes in object detection algorithms that have a high overlap with other bounding boxes. It is often used as a post-processing step after object detection has been performed, to help ensure that only the most relevant and distinct object bounding boxes are retained. The object detection algorithm produces a set of bounding boxes, each with an associated confidence score indicating how confident the algorithm is that the box contains an object.

The NMS algorithm takes the set of bounding boxes and iterates through them, comparing each box to the other boxes in the set. For each pair of bounding boxes, the NMS algorithm calculates the overlap between the two boxes. If the overlap is above a certain threshold (e.g., 50%), then one of the boxes is considered a "duplicate" of the other and is removed. The NMS algorithm continues iterating through the bounding boxes and removing duplicates until all the boxes are processed.

Before Non-Maximum Suppression

After Non-Maximum Suppression

Fig. 2. Effect of Non-Maximum Suppression.

Fig. 2 describes that the main goal of NMS is to retain only the bounding boxes that are the most distinct and relevant, while removing those that are redundant or have a low confidence score. This helps to improve the overall accuracy and efficiency of the object detection algorithm and also makes it look clean and representable.

Algorithm 1. Classification of features

Input: Video to perform object detection

Output:

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- 1. Reading input video.
- 2. Loading YOLO v3 Network
- 3. Reading frames in the loop
- 4. Getting blob from the frame
- 5. Implementing Forward Pass
- 6. Getting Bounding Boxes
- 7. Drawing Bounding Boxes with Labels
- 8. Writing processed frames

3. Results

In terms of accuracy, YOLOv3 has been shown to outperform many other object detection algorithms, particularly on small objects and objects with unusual shapes or poses. It is also able to detect objects at multiple scales, which is important for detecting objects of varying sizes in an image. In terms of efficiency, YOLOv3 is able to process images in real-time, making it suitable for applications where speed is important. The YOLOv3 algorithm deployed in the proposed system has proven to give a accuracy of 95.33%. It is also able to run on a variety of hardware, including CPUs, GPUs, and specialized hardware such as Google's Tensor Processing Units (TPUs). When the object is detected a bounding box appears in that object, different types of objects having different colors and the name of the predicted object is written on top of the bounding box and also the confidence of the system or we can also say the probability is written as well which changes as the object moves.

5. Conclusions

With Overall, YOLOv3 is a fast and accurate object detection algorithm that is well-suited for real-time applications. It has a high frame rate and can detect a wide variety of objects in different shapes and sizes. YOLOv3 works well on a variety of data, including images and video frames, and can be trained to recognize a wide range of objects. It can also handle occlusion and partial visibility of objects. One of the main strengths of YOLOv3 is its ability to process images and videos in real-time, making it suitable for applications such as security, self-driving cars and assistive system for the blind where quick decision-making is critical. However, YOLOv3 may

not always perform optimally in all situations. For example, it may struggle with low-light environments or complex scenes with a large number of objects. In summary, YOLOv3 is a powerful object detection algorithm that can be used in a variety of applications. Its high speed and accuracy make it a valuable tool for real-time object detection tasks.

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